

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ELECTRON DENSITY OF THE LOWER IONOSPHERE AS FOUND THROUGH MULTIMODE TWEAK-ATMOSPHERICS: RANKING OF THE INPUT PARAMETERS BY SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

Tweek-atmospherics (tweeks), along with radio transmission by VLF radio stations, are used to study the lower ionosphere. The new single-position method for determining of electron density in the lower ionosphere by multimodal tweek-atmospherics is studied upon the numerical simulations. The electron density profile model in the nighttime atmospherics (tweeks) approach aims to more closely represent the physical profile of the *D*-layer nighttime ionosphere. It corresponds to a layer of constant electron density at least 8...10 km thick and a much lower electron density below it. The influence of five main variable parameters on the sought-for electron density for realistic natural values of the parameters was numerically studied. The main influence has been shown to be exerted by the difference in the effective reflection heights of the first and second harmonics of tweek-atmospheric. It is shown that the scope of applicability of this method can be expanded taking into account the different scale of the contribution of variable parameters. It is shown that failure to correctly account for the polarization of the tweeks could result in the true electron concentration being about 25% of the calculated one.

Keywords: lower ionosphere diagnostic, tweek-atmospherics, ELF – VLF radiowaves, lightning location.

1. Introduction

Electromagnetic pulse radiation which has been excited by the lightning stroke has a maximum spectral density at extra low frequencies range (ELF, 300...3000 Hz) and very low frequencies (VLF, 3...30 kHz). The Earth-ionosphere cavity serves as a waveguide for electromagnetic waves in these frequency ranges. At night, so-called tweek atmospherics, or tweeks, are often observed. They are characterized by a longer duration than that of daytime atmospherics, up to 10...100 ms. In the spectrogram of the tweek, the initial part is a linearly polarized broadband signal, then a number of individual harmonics are observed, and their instantaneous frequencies decrease, asymptotically approaching roughly multiples of the cutoff frequencies of the waveguide. Along with radio transmission by VLF radio stations, the use of these natural signals gives a possibility to study a layer of ionosphere at altitudes of 60...90 km with a low electron concentration ($10^6...10^9 \text{ m}^{-3}$).

The *D*-region (~60–90 km) is the lowest layer of Earth's ionosphere, and its current state of ionization is a much stronger function of the current solar state [1, p. 1276] due to much greater recombination rate. Some nighttime ionosphere is maintained by background extrasolar radiation such as Ly- α (121.57 nm) [2, p. 547]. Responding quickly to a host of geophysical phenomena, *D*-region is in essence a large natural detector, particularly at nighttime where the ionization is quite low (few electrons per cm^3).

Unfortunately, the *D*-region is also difficult to directly measure because the neutral atmospheric density causes too much drag on satellites, but is not dense enough for balloon traverses. Rocket-based measurements have been successful in making in-situ measurements, but are expensive and episodic [3, p. 145]. In addition, the relatively low electron density causes weak reflections of radar-based techniques, which are also difficult to generate due to the long wavelength of

frequencies below the *D*-region plasma frequency. Incoherent scatter radar (ISR) and partial-reflection techniques have been able to make quality measurements but only with careful treatment and with limited time resolution [4, p. 137].

There exist a number of very low frequency and low frequency (VLF/LF, 3...30 and 3...300 kHz) transmitters whose signals propagate to global distances by reflecting off of the *D*-region of the ionosphere and the Earth ground forming the Earth-ionosphere waveguide (EIWG) [5]. These transmitters are used for global and subsea communications. The classical [6] two-parameter model is used as standard approach to specify an ionospheric electron density profile model as input to a VLF propagation model. The development and validation of the Wait-Spies model [6] took place using almost exclusively narrowband VLF/LF transmitters with the primary intention of predicting VLF/LF signal amplitude and phase from said transmitters. The Wait-Spies exponential model is known to be highly simplified but is often the best we can do, and has been used in countless VLF/LF remote sensing scientific investigations.

Many studies utilizing narrow frequency signals to produce ionospheric inferences have found good agreement between data and model for day and night ([7, p. 831], [8], [9, p. 6865], [10]). Furthermore, some have used the VLF/LF broadband emissions from lightning to make remote inferences of the *D*-region with good agreement at night [11, p. 1781]. The Wait-Spies model should not be viewed as an accurate representation of the actual *D*-region of the ionosphere, but rather a mathematical model that best reproduces VLF propagation at a specific frequency. It's specified as:

$$N_e(h) = 1.43 * 10^7 \exp(-0.15h') * \exp[(\beta - 0.15)(h - h')] \text{ cm}^{-3},$$

where h' and β can be understood as the “height” and “steepness” of the D -region.

In recent work, McCormick and Cohen [12] introduced a new four-parameter model of the D -region ionospheric electron density (60–90 km) relevant to the wide-band very low frequency (VLF, 3–30 kHz) pulsed radio signals (atmospherics or sferics). This model was aimed at representing the electron density closer to the physical profile and consistent with the data on the sferics propagation. Its exponential height profile of electron density linked to the classical work [6] contains a split by 5...8 km around the altitude of 60...65 km in the daytime with the constant electron density. All data relate to summer and autumn in the tropics of the northern hemisphere. The lack of nighttime sensitivity to the split is consistent with the FIRI profiles [13, p. 6737], which indicate a split at nighttime at 90...100 km by ~10 km and up ~50 km with 1000...3000 particles/cm³, so typically outside the range of electron densities that VLF radio waves by this methodic are sensitive to.

A set of height profiles of air conductivity have been developed for explaining Schumann resonance (SR) data and the data of global current circuit ([14], [15, p. 1], [16, p. 105], [17], [18]), namely the averaged SR profile [14] and the SR ambient day and night profiles used in the paper [18] by Nickolaenko et al.

For the topic of our work it is significant that such a global profile in the daytime is very close to model [12] at the 60...90 km layer, and at night a layer with a slow increase in conductivity is detected at altitudes of 90...100 km by global means of Schumann resonance. These parameters are in good agreement with the results of rocket measurements of the electron density profiles [13], which demonstrated very steep growth of electron concentration from 1 to ~1000 cm⁻³ in the altitude interval 80...90 km combined with much slower variations at higher altitudes.

The electron density profile model in the nighttime atmospherics (tweaks) approach [19, p. 94] also aims to more closely represent the physical profile of the D -layer nighttime ionosphere. It corresponds to a layer of constant electron density at least 8...10 km thick and a much lower electron density below it.

Tweak atmospherics have been singled out as a special subspecies of atmospherics due to their extremely long duration [20, p. 1476]. The use of a waveguide model with isotropic conducting boundaries made it possible to satisfactorily explain the dispersion properties of tweaks [21, p. 58]. A number of tweak peculiarities were discovered later, namely: tweaks are recorded when the signal source and receiver are at night conditions, or even during a solar eclipse [22, p. 667]; the polarization of the tweak signal in the final, so-called tail part is typically close to left-circular polarization. Extra long tweak tails are also poorly explained by isotropic waveguide model. These facts can be explained using theory from [23, p. 151], [24, p. 60], [25, p. 1363], [26, p. 33].

Due to such a theory, the new method for determining of electron density in the lower ionosphere by results of analysis of multimodal tweak-atmospherics was described in detail and probed also in [19, p. 94].

This evaluation method is based on determining reflection heights both for the fundamental and second tweak harmonics. So, only tweak records highly likely to include two or more harmonics are usable in this technique.

The reflection heights of tweak's first and second harmonics one can find by an improved modification of the single-position (so-called "Kharkiv") method for lightning location and estimation of the lower ionosphere height by tweak-atmospherics which is described in detail in [27, p. 53], [28, p. 40]. The stages of the modified technique are as follows: calculation of the dynamic spectra (sonograms) of a signal based on its parts of variable length, which is determined by preliminary estimations of the path parameters of a given tweak; isolation of signal harmonics in the sonogram and automatic selection of tweak parameters that give satisfactory approximations of the observed tweak harmonics for one of the three signal components. Algorithm [27, p. 53], [28, p. 40] was tested on model tweak waveforms; it has shown to achieve very good agreement between the model and calculated parameters of the tweak path up to 8 Mm [28, p. 40], [29, p. 289].

The East – West asymmetry of first quasi-transverse electric (QTE) mode propagation with frequencies ~2...3 kHz in the Earth-ionosphere waveguide is known from observations of atmospherics [30, p. 1491], [31, p. 101]. The azimuthal dependence was revealed [32, p. 461], [33, p. 20] in the tweak polarization at the first harmonic, where it manifested itself at source distances of 1.5...4.5 Mm as non-reciprocity of East – West propagation, also later there was observed [34, p. 44] an azimuthal dependence in the tweak spectra, i.e., the number of tweak harmonics at source distances of 8...10 Mm, according to the experimental records database accumulated at the Ukrainian Antarctic Station "Akademik Vernadsky" in 2019 – 2021. Tweak-atmospherics in this database have source ranges from 1.5 Mm to 10 Mm or more. The same method [19, p. 94] has been used to estimate an electron density at reflection layer in lower ionosphere by these data [35, p. 116].

For example, at the same night in late March of 2019, three active thunderstorm cells might be distinguished: one is found in the Atlantic Ocean with the center at a distance of 5500 km and an azimuth of ~45° (more than 1300 specimen rich), the other is positioned near the La Plata coast at a distance of ~2900 km from the Antarctic observatory with azimuth ~15° and has roughly 100 specimen within, and third one is observed nearby the south-east coast of Africa at a distance of 7200 km and an azimuth of ~110° with ~1000 tweak recordings, and there was recorded enough tweaks with second harmonic from all three thunderstorm cells to estimate the plasma density in low ionosphere by each.

Within the frequency range of 1.6...20 kHz, up to 9 harmonics are revealed in the experimental recordings of tweak atmospherics. On the experimental material, it was previously shown that at source distances of more than 1.5 Mm and less than 4.5 Mm the tweaks have 2...4 harmonics in the spectrum. The ratios of the reflection and attenuation parameters in the lower ionosphere, as well as the background noise level, lead to

the fact that, for source distances to the receiver about 10 Mm and more, tweek harmonics, except for the fundamental one, are usually not observed.

The ELF – VLF waves propagate over long distances with low attenuation. The emissions in this range are mainly provided by two sources – natural and man-made. The natural source of these emissions is global lightning activity (GLA), the main three centers of which are located in the equatorial regions of Southeast Asia, Africa and America. With the receiving station located in the circumpolar region, where there are no local thunderstorms and any industrial activity, the single-position registration of tweek-atmospherics is therefore practically advantageous for global monitoring and receives radio signals from at least two world centers. The single-position method for finding the parameters of the lower ionosphere, the main of which should be recognized as the electron density at the height of the ionospheric reflecting layer, is a powerful tool that can be widely used in research of EIWG. As an initial stage for the needs of practical measurements, it is useful to determine and describe the features of the method under conditions where it is impossible to ensure the same accuracy in determining all factor parameters that participate in finding the value of the electron concentration. The purpose of this work is to predict the behavior of the method under conditions of realistic input parameters using computational simulation and, based on these predictions, to formulate practical recommendations.

In Section 2 we describe the algorithm for finding the electron density and characteristic heights of its profile. Section 3 presents numerical simulations of the operation of such an algorithm for the heights of the ionospheric *D*-layer and the lower *E*-layer, 80...100 km. In section 4 we present simplified formulas obtained with a small Δh parameter – the difference between the effective reflection heights of the first and second harmonics of the tweek-atmospheric. Section 5 includes the ranking of the input parameters by the size of their contribution to the variation of the calculated electron density, where the parameters also include the tweek's path-dependent geomagnetic field and tweek polarization. An example of processing a data set illustrating such an influence of parameters is described. In Section 6 conclusions are given.

2. Algorithm for finding the ionospheric electron density

A method for analyzing the tweeks [27, p. 53], [36, p. 37], [37, p. 789] allows to estimate the cut off frequencies and respective effective heights of the Earth-ionosphere waveguide in the ELF – VLF range for the fundamental and the higher order waveguide modes. It was shown in the works [36, p. 37], [38, p. 1], [39, p. 14], [40, p. 1], [41, p. 20] based on the analysis of the experimental tweek records, that with an increase in the mode number and, accordingly, the frequency of the incident wave, the effective height of the waveguide decreases. That is explained by a decrease in the penetration depth of the low-frequency wave into the ionosphere with increasing frequency.

An approximate theory has been developed [24, p. 60], [25, p. 1363], [26, p. 33], [42, p. 1185], in which

the features are considered of formation of the tweek field at night conditions in the ionosphere near the critical frequencies of the waveguide. The assumptions about the boundary conditions in the Earth-ionosphere waveguide in this model are such that they are satisfied almost everywhere on the geoid, except for a narrow band near the geomagnetic equator. The results of measurements from experimental recordings of nighttime tweek-atmospherics are therefore interpreted according to such a model in the following discussion.

The following assumptions have been used in the model of the Earth-ionosphere waveguide to obtain analytical dependences connecting the propagation parameters of the ELF – VLF radio waves with the parameters of the ionospheric plasma. The waveguide is assumed to be infinite and flat with perfectly conducting Earth. The following condition is satisfied for the nighttime lower ionosphere at frequencies $f \leq 5$ kHz: $\omega \ll \nu \ll \omega_{Be}$, where ω is the circular frequency of the incident wave, ν is the collision frequency of electrons with neutral particles, $\omega_{Be} = \frac{eB_0}{m_e}$ is the electron gyrofrequency [in SI system], B_0 is the geomagnetic field induction, e is the electron charge, m_e is mass of electron. Calculations were carried out using a model of a uniform [homogeneous] sharply bounded ionosphere with a lower boundary found at the height h_E [24, p. 60], [25, p. 1363]. The quasi-longitudinal approximation is applied in propagation of low-frequency radio waves in the ionosphere, which is satisfied under the condition: $\tan I \gg \omega|\omega_{Be}|/2\omega_{pe}^2$, where I is the inclination angle, ω_{pe} is the electron plasma frequency.

The critical frequencies of the quasi-transverse electric normal waves (left-handed polarized), prevailing in the tweek field [23, p. 151], are expressed as follows [24, p. 60], [25, p. 1363]:

$$f_{cm} = \frac{cm}{2h_E} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\pi m \mu}\right), \quad (1)$$

where c is the light velocity in vacuum; m is the mode number; $\mu = \omega/\sqrt{\omega_{pe}|\omega_B \sin I|}$ is the refraction index, μ must be considered at effective reflection height of tweek, so in this expression a circular frequency ω is examined at tweek tail and is equal to $\omega_m = 2\pi f_m$, where effective cut-off frequency $f_m = \frac{cm}{2h_E}$.

We can obtain estimates of the height h_E and electron concentration N_e at the height h_E from formula (1) using the measured cut off frequencies of the 1st and the 2nd order modes, f_{c1} and f_{c2} respectively, determined from a tweek record:

$$h_E = \frac{c}{2f_1}, f_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}-1} \left(\frac{f_{c2}}{\sqrt{2}} - f_{c1} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$N_e = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2 m_e \epsilon_0}{e^2}, \omega_{pe}^2 = \frac{2|\omega_{Be} \sin I|}{\pi} * \frac{f_1^3}{(f_1 - f_{c1})^2}. \quad (3)$$

In these formulae electric constant $\epsilon_0 = 8.854$ F/m.

III. The numerical simulations.

Let's make some considerations about the influence of main factor parameters on the estimates according to formula (3) through the model calculations. According to (3), N_e is directly proportional to $\sin I$ and gyrofrequency of electrons ω_{Be} , and therefore, $N_e \propto B_0$.

The dependence on the cutoff frequencies of the two lowest modes from (2) can be represented as a dependence on the effective reflection heights of these modes, or, equivalently, as a dependence on one of the heights and on their difference Δh . The penetration depths l_1 and l_2 of the first and second tweak harmonics (corresponding to order modes) into the ionosphere have a difference between them (and, accordingly, a difference in the effective reflection heights Δh), which is

nonlinearly related to the resulting parameters of expressions (2) and (3). Fig. 1 shows the effective lower boundary of the ionosphere h_E (diamonds) and the corresponding characteristic frequency f_1 (crosses), when the mentioned difference Δh changes from 0.5 km to 4 km in increments of 0.5 km. The height range covers the entire range of 80...100 km, which is significant for practice.

Figure 1. Model parameters for different values of height difference.

It is easy to see that the difference Δh is small compared to the heights h_1 and h_2 . As a result the dependencies are close to linear which will be discussed below. Now let's calculate the electron concentration in the ionospheric layer at the reflection height. The model height differences Δh are the same as before. In Fig. 2, the dependences of the electron concentration on the reflection height of the second harmonic are located along lines close to straight lines. We use in the computations the average over the propagation path geomagnetic field inclination $I = -52^\circ$ and two values of

the total geomagnetic field induction $B_0 = 30000$ nT (black rhombs) and 22000 nT (grey rhombs). Fig.2 shows the calculation results on a logarithmic scale, since changes in the height difference by 1...2 km lead to concentration variations of up to an order of magnitude. Moreover, changing altitude results in significantly smaller effects on N_e . This effect decreases slightly with increasing height difference – from 15.7% of the average concentration value for an height difference of 0.5 km to approximately 11% of the average value for an height difference of up to 4 km.

Figure 2. Electron concentration for different values of height difference.

IV. Approximate formulas and discussion.

A numerical simulation study showed that the model value of concentration is approximately inversely proportional to the $(\Delta h)^2$, and the smaller Δh , the more N_e tends to the value $\propto 1/(\Delta h)^2$.

Simplifying the formulas in the small Δh approximation is useful for further consideration. All realistic estimates of the value of h_2 fall within the range of 80...100 km, and Δh does not exceed 4...5 km, therefore, the condition $\Delta h \ll h_2$ is satisfied. It can be easily shown that then, according to (2):

$$h_E \approx h_2 - \frac{\Delta h}{\sqrt{2}-1} \cong h_2 - 2.41\Delta h, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{f_1^3}{(f_1 - f_{c1})^2} \approx \frac{ch_2(\sqrt{2}-1)^2}{4\Delta h^2}. \quad (5)$$

After substituting (5) into (3) we get:

$$N_e \cong \frac{\varepsilon_0 c (\sqrt{2}-1)^2}{2\pi e \cdot \Delta h^2} |B_0 \sin I| h_2 = 4.53 \cdot 10^8 |B_0 \sin I| h_2 / \Delta h^2 [\text{particles/cm}^3]. \quad (6)$$

An approximation (6) should not be used instead of the exact formulas (2), (3), which are easy to calculate. It helps to evaluate the form of dependence on factor parameters in (2), (3).

From these data and formulas it can be inferred that the experimental determination of the effective reflection heights in itself does not impact the concentration assessment and the systematic error in the height assessment will not introduce significant distortions into the concentration calculation as long as this error

is the same for the first and second harmonics. This reasoning applies, in particular, to the case of large distances. The overestimation of the heights for distances of 8...10 Mm due to the peculiarities of the computational algorithm keeps on the height difference Δh in approximately the same range of values.

Previously [29, p. 289], it was concluded that the assessment of the reflection heights h of ELF waves in the ionosphere by tweaks for a distance to their sources of 8 Mm and more can be carried out with great caution and only as an approximate evaluation. At the same time, as one can deduce from the analysis, this technique of ionospheric concentration estimation can be used when working with tweak groups at distances of 8...10 Mm and more. The error in determining the heights introduces a negligible error for N_e of about 11...15% over the entire practically important range.

V. The ranking of input parameters.

Let us compare Δh effect with the change in electron density values N_e , which, according to the model, is introduced by taking into account the magnitude of the geomagnetic field B_0 and the angle of geomagnetic field inclination I due to the specific location of the tweak-atmospheric path from the excitation point to the receiver. A decrease in the magnetic field from 30 000 nT to 22 000 nT (the minimum value in the South Atlantic Anomaly) proportionally reduces the concentration value by approximately 25% (see in Fig.2). Since the technique using tweaks is incorrect to use for tweak paths over a narrow region around the geomagnetic equator, where the angle I is less than 15° , then, if we assume that the receiver is located, for example, at the "Akademik Vernadsky" station, the average angle I

along the tweek path can vary from approximately 58° for eastern paths to 37° for the paths from north used in evaluation. This means that the dependence on the sine of the angle I can introduce a further 30% change in the concentration value.

In sum, for equal reflection heights, the calculated concentration value can be reduced by approximately half for tweek paths from the north compared to paths from the east.

Thus, for realistic values of the parameters, taking these factors into account produces concentration values that are of the same order of magnitude. This influence is significantly lower than the influence of Δh , the variation of which within realistic limits leads to changes in concentration from 70 particles per cubic centimeter to several thousand particles per cubic centimeter.

It is also necessary to discuss the influence of such a parameter as tweek polarization. Formulas (2) and (3) use expressions for modes of left-handed circular polarization (L -modes). The theoretical model from [24, p. 60], [25, p. 1363] also gives expressions for the cut-off frequencies of the mode with right-handed circular polarization. The penetration depth of these modes into the ionosphere is approximately an order of magnitude less than for L -modes, given the usual ratio of the collision frequency of charged particles with neutrals and the gyrofrequency of electrons at the height of reflection of these waves in the ionosphere.

When discussing the applicability limits of the method for estimating the ionospheric concentration through tweeks, it was pointed out [19, p. 94] that to improve accuracy it is necessary to control the polarization of tweeks and apply the calculation algorithm for groups of atmospherics with a predominance of left-hand polarization. Let us estimate how large a relative error can be introduced by failure to comply with this requirement. This need arises when working with data arrays that contain only distances and reflection heights calculated from the frequency dispersion curves of tweek signals, and there are no records of the signal itself. Let us first assume that we do not know the ratio in the ensemble of tweeks with left circular polarization and tweeks with non-left circular polarization. In this case, we will assume the share of both types of tweeks for the instance of the greatest dispersion, that is, 50% of some and 50% of others.

It should be noted the natural experiments factually display that the non-reciprocity of tweek propagation is manifested in their polarization [32, p. 461], [33, p. 20]. When tweeks coming from the east propagate in middle latitudes over long distances, the proportion of left-polarized radiation in the tweek signal decreases and the polarization shifts to the near-linear one. Linear polarization means that the relative proportions of left-handed circular (L -modes) and right-handed circular

(R -modes) in the tweek's radiation are equal. The existing theoretical explanation of this fact [42, p. 1185] takes into account the influence of the angle between the Poynting vector of the tweek and the geomagnetic field lines on the attenuation coefficients of the L - and R -modes. Since we are dealing with a statistical process when calculating the average reflection height of the tweek harmonics, we can equivalently replace the temporal distribution (the signal of a single tweek) with a spatial distribution (the ensemble of simultaneous tweeks). Thus, for tweeks from the eastern sector, the theoretical limit is also 50% of samples with left-handed circular polarization and 50% with right-handed circular polarization.

Keeping in mind that the penetration depth of R -modes is approximately 10 times smaller, we conclude that the penetration depths of the first harmonic found for the group of tweeks will be about $\sim 0.55 l_1$ at the very least. The same is true for l_2 . This results in a 45% reduction in Δh . The smaller Δh is, the greater the relative effect on the calculation of the electron concentration, based on the model (see Fig. 2). The overestimation of the concentration is from 300 particles per cubic centimeter (instead of 80) to 4000 (instead of 1000) and on average N_e will be 3.5...4 times greater.

According to this analysis, failure to correctly account for the polarization of the tweeks could result in the true electron concentration being about 25% of the calculated one. That is, the concentration may be overestimated, but approximately the same order of magnitude.

The intricate question is how often and in what circumstances such an effect should be taken into account. Tweek-atmospherics registered in high and middle geomagnetic latitudes have left-handed circular polarization as a rule. This is their specific feature [23, p. 151]. The effect of non-reciprocal propagation is clearly manifested for tweeks in a narrow sector of arrival azimuths, according to field measurements [33, p. 20]. Such a special section can be approximately considered to be the angle between the direction of signal propagation and the geomagnetic meridian of $90^\circ \pm 15^\circ$. The non-reciprocity of the propagation of ELF – VLF waves is also recorded in the spectra of night atmospherics; in this azimuth range, they more often have the second and higher harmonics in the signal composition with equal path lengths compared to tweeks with other azimuths [34, p. 44].

Apparently, we can limit ourselves to considering the issue of polarization only for a certain azimuth sector. In such areas, it is necessary to remember that the true Δh is most likely greater than the measured one and the electron concentration is lower. An increased percentage of tweek-atmospherics with a second harmonic at long distances may indirectly indicate the presence of propagation non-reciprocity.

Figure 3. Effective reflection heights for tweeks during 0...9 hours UTC, 12 February 2021.

Fig. 3 illustrates one of the sets of data of this kind that are subject to study. Measurements at the “Akademik Vernadsky” station were made on the night when the geomagnetic situation was extremely quiet, the three-hour planetary index $K_p = 0...1$. The entire set of measured effective reflection heights of the first (fundamental) harmonic of tweeks is shown depending on the distance to the tweek source (small triangles). In addition, the measured data of effective reflection heights for several thunderstorm cells are shown, where the azimuths of the cell center are of about 15° (small crosses), 30° (large triangles) and 100° (large stars – the 1st harmonic, large rhombs – the 2nd harmonic). The same Fig.3 shows (in the form of pentangular stars of different colors) moving average for the first and second harmonics of the thunderstorm cells from azimuths 30° and 100° . It can be seen that on the azimuth of 30° the height difference Δh was $0.75...1$ km on a large interval of distances $4...5.7$ Mm and was slightly larger, up to 1.5 km, for distances $5.8...6.2$ Mm. (For a moving average, areas from the near and far edge of dataset should not be taken into account.) For thunderstorm cell with the azimuth of 100° , the far edge of dataset was not depicted. The linear fits for the reflection heights of the first (dashed line) and second (solid line) harmonics for the thunderstorm cell with the azimuth of 100° are given. It can be seen that they significantly do not coincide with the estimates received through the moving average. By moving average in this example, Δh estimates are approximately ~ 0.5 km – on $8...8.5$ Mm, $0.8...1$ km – on $8.5...9.1$ Mm, $1.5...1.7$ km – on $9.2...9.7$ Mm, and ~ 1.2 km – on $9.8...10$ Mm. It should be noted that the height differences Δh were smaller at the largest distances than at somewhat smaller distances.

Through expressions (2), (3) described above, the electron density profile evaluations can be obtained. The values of the geomagnetic inclination I and geomagnetic field magnitude B_0 were taken as 50° and $26\ 000$ nT and 55° and $30\ 000$ nT for azimuths of 30° and 100° , respectively. In the direction to thunderstorm

with the azimuth of 30° , the ionosphere should have an electronic density of $800...1400$ particles/cm³ above the boundary which varies between 86 km and 87 km for distances $4...5.2$ Mm, and is increasing with a distance from 87 km to 89 km for slightly large distances $5.2...5.7$ Mm. The noticeably smaller electronic density about $350...550$ particles/cm³ should be above the boundary increasing from 87.8 km to 88.8 km at distances $5.8...6.2$ Mm. Thus, in general, with distance the height of the boundary h_E increases (by 3 km, i.e. 3%), while the electron density has decreased (by about 3 times).

Contrary to that, in the case of the azimuth of 100° the boundary height h_E is decreasing with distance – $87.8...88.3$ km for distance range $8...8.5$ Mm, $87.1...87.6$ km for $8.5...9.1$ Mm, $86...86.5$ km for $9.2...9.7$ Mm, and only for distance range from 9.8 Mm to 10 Mm it's increasing from 87.6 km to 90 km. The electronic density values above these boundaries should be ~ 3900 particles/cm³, $\sim 1000...1500$ particles/cm³, $330...400$ particles/cm³, and for the last range ~ 680 particles/cm³, respectively. It should be noted that the true electron concentration can be about 25% of the calculated one. The decrease in both the electron density and lower boundary of the reflecting layer in this case may be due to the fact that local time in the direction to east of the reception station changes and the sources of tweeks are closer to local dawn and the terminator.

As a result of the analysis, the factor parameters when calculating the electron density from equations (2) and (3) can be ranked. The main influence is exerted by the difference Δh in the effective reflection heights of the first and second harmonics. The specific location of the tweek path has a significant, but much smaller effect of 75% to 25% on the electron density, due to the magnitude of the magnetic field, the angle of magnetic inclination, and possible variations in polarization. The least influence is exerted by the reflection height itself, introducing variations of only $10...15\%$.

The above conclusion should be applied to the choice between alternative statistical approaches. To best estimate the electron density, the nonlinearity of the dependencies must be taken into account. It is preferable to abstain from the option of calculating the electron density for each individual tweek with two harmonics, and only then averaging over the sample. It is more advantageous to perform averaging over a sample for linear parameters h_1 and h_2 in order to evaluate Δh as accurately as possible. The number of tweeks involved in the evaluation of h_1 and h_2 may likely differ.

On the contrary, when calculating the model lower boundary of the reflecting layer of the lower ionosphere (its height is designated above as h_E) in the approximation of small Δh , the dependence on both the heights and Δh is linear. Nevertheless, the possible contribution of the measurement error of Δh is 2.4 times greater than that for the reflection heights, therefore the determination of h_E also requires the most careful determination of Δh .

VI. Conclusions.

The method for estimating the electron concentration in the reflective layer of the lower ionosphere using natural ELF – VLF signals (night tweek-atmospherics) has a finite accuracy, which can be increased by choosing a method for statistical processing of incoming data.

The influence of five main variable parameters on the sought-for electron density for realistic natural values of the parameters was numerically studied. The main influence has been shown to be exerted by the difference Δh in the effective reflection heights of the first and second harmonics. The model value of electron density is approximately inversely proportional to the $(\Delta h)^2$, and the smaller Δh , the more electron density N_e tends to the value $\propto 1/(\Delta h)^2$.

The specific location of the tweek path has a significant, but much smaller effect of 75% to 25% on the electron density, due to the magnitude of the magnetic field, the angle of magnetic inclination, and possible variations in tweek polarization. The least influence is exerted by the reflection height itself, introducing variations of only 10...15%.

It is shown that the scope of applicability of this method can be expanded taking into account the different scale of the contribution of parameters. The electron density can be estimated, including such a cases (tweek paths 8...11 Mm long), when the method gives an over-estimated effective reflection height. It is shown that failure to correctly account for the polarization of the tweeks could result in the true electron concentration being about 25% of the calculated one. This effect needs to be relegated except the case of non-reciprocal propagation for tweeks in a narrow sector of arrival azimuths where the angle between the direction of signal propagation and the geomagnetic meridian is of $90^\circ \pm 15^\circ$. An increased percentage of tweeks with a second harmonic at long signal paths may indirectly indicate the presence of propagation non-reciprocity.

Within the realistic values of the input parameters, the calculated values of electron density lie in the range from several tens to several thousand particles/cm³ at radio wave reflection heights from 80 to 100 km. These

parameters are in good agreement with the results of rocket measurements of the electron density profiles [13, p. 6737], which demonstrated very steep growth of electron concentration from 1 to ~ 1000 cm⁻³ in the altitude interval 80...90 km combined with much slower variations at higher altitudes.

Due to the nonlinearity of Δh influence, it is recommended to determine the effective reflection heights by averaging on statistical large arrays (at least 20 specimens), and then proceed to calculate the electron density. With this approach, rare cases when the effective reflection height of the first mode is lower than that of the second mode can also participate in the computational algorithm.

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